

ASSESSMENT OF DNA EXTRACTION EFFICIENCY USING DIFFERENT SWAB DEVICES IN MODERN FORENSIC INVESTIGATIONS

**¹Nelson Chioma Stellamaris, ²Onyia Christie O, ³Paschaleen Onyemaechi
and ⁴Uchenna N. Urom**

*^{1,2,3}Department of Biological Sciences and Environmental Studies, Godfrey Okoye University, Enugu
Nigeria*

⁴Inqaba Biotec. West Africa Ltd

Email: *chiomasnelson@gmail.com / onyia01@hotmail.com / paschaleen@gouni.edu.ng /
uchenna.urom@inqababiotec.africa*

Phone: *+2348083010380, 0009-0009-2853-434X, +2347068248367, +2347062412439*

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15188760>

Abstract:

Objective: *DNA analysis is an important tool for crime conviction or human exoneration. Swab devices are used to collect body fluids, including buccal samples, for forensic testing and analysis. They are made of different materials and are differently shaped, which may impact on the quality of the DNA that can be recovered from the body fluids absorbed by the swabs. In this study, commercially available swabs used for COVID-19 testing in Nigeria were used to collect buccal samples and analyzed using Nanodrop spectrophotometry to determine the quality, quantity and purity of extracted DNA.*

Method: *The buccal cavity of an individual was examined for any open wounds or incisions with gloves on after which the internal cheek was swabbed for 60 seconds on each side using the swab tool. The swabbing process was carried out thrice and the samples were processed.*

Results: *The analysis for each swab type was carried out thrice. Swabs with optimal sampling efficacy also demonstrated superior efficiency in the extraction process. The oral swab performed best with an efficiency of 82%. The cotton swab performed second best with an efficiency of 67%. Statistical analysis (ANOVA) indicated a significant difference between at least two swab devices, since the p-value was less than the significance value of 0.05.*

Conclusions: *Based on the results of swabs tested, nylon-flocked swabs and cotton swabs are better recommended for sampling and collection of body fluids for forensic applications, with the oral swab being an appropriate choice, and the cotton swab as a suitable alternative.*

Keywords: *Forensic testing, swab devices, absorption capacity, extraction efficiency, DNA analysis, buccal sample, sample collection*

1. Introduction

Forensic science serves as a bridge between crime and science. It assists investigators in inspecting all significant cases and is also an important instrument for court outcomes. The advancement of forensic science services is clearly dependent on the investigators grasping the breadth, significance, and limitations of forensic science (Anam, *et al.*, 2019).

Subsequent technological advances have made it possible to create highly discriminating profiles from a variety of biological sources relatively quickly and inexpensively, while also ensuring uniformity across jurisdictions and the construction of a comprehensive database of genetic information. The identification of catastrophe victims and missing persons has also benefited increasingly from the use of the same approaches (Van-Oorschot, *et al.*, 2018).

Forensic analysis of biological evidence through biotechnological approaches is gaining significance in criminal inquiries, encompassing the realm of wildlife poaching offenses (Onyia, *et al.*, 2021). Prior until now, the majority of forensic analysis was the examination of biological samples taken from crime scenes. Traditional forensic investigation techniques include the examination of biological evidence such as blood proteins (serology), other bodily fluids including sweat, urine, and saliva, and body tissues like blood (Divakar, 2017).

The stages involved in DNA extraction consists of the following steps:

- Disruption of cytoplasmic and nuclear membranes;
- Isolation of DNA and its purification from other cellular lysate constituents like lipids, proteins, and additional nucleic acids.
- Concentration and purification of DNA (Ali, *et al.*, 2017).

The use of biotechnology tool in forensic investigation gave rise to a new branch of forensic science known as Forensic Biotechnology. Utilizing this technique for DNA sample analysis facilitates accurate identifications, even from extremely small traces of evidence gathered at the crime scene. Deoxyribonucleic acid, also known as DNA, is a double-helixed molecular structure. One must have in-depth knowledge of DNA structure in order to completely comprehend the role of DNA analysis. The nucleotide triphosphate molecules serve as the foundation of this structure. A triphosphate group, a deoxyribose sugar, and a nucleotide base make up these molecules. These four nucleotide bases can be categorized as purine bases or pyrimidine bases, according to differences in their structural makeup (Syed, *et al.*, 2018).

Forensic biotechnology is commonly linked to DNA fingerprinting. With the aid of forensic biotechnology, an expert can examine the traces—such as blood or fingerprints—obtained from the

crime scene in comparison to traces from other types of reference evidence, such as items discovered on a suspect's property or the victim (Dumache, *et al.*, 2016). Colin Pitchfork became the initial individual apprehended as a result of a DNA analysis. He committed sexual assaults against two girls, Lynda and Dawn, leading to their tragic deaths in 1983 and 1986, respectively. To conclusively resolve the case, law enforcement obtained sperm samples, subjecting them to forensic scrutiny. Colin admitted to his wrongdoing, and his arrest ensued when DNA evidence conclusively identified him as the perpetrator (Roewer, 2013).

The new field of DNA forensics is now being transformed radically and fundamentally in many aspects of criminal investigation which include:

- i. DNA fingerprinting;
- ii. DNA foot-printing;
- iii. DNA profiling. (Dumache, *et al.*, 2016)

DNA fingerprinting is a chemical test that reveals a living being's genetic make-up. This genetic makeup is implemented in paternity tests, genetic profiling of an individual within a species, comparing differences between individuals of different species, determining sex, classifying inherited diseases, identifying victims (by comparing profiles of victims with reference samples), determining victim identity, tracking threatened species, classifying inherited diseases, and conserving biological diversity. In this facet of DNA forensics, chemicals are employed to disentangle DNA strands, unveiling distinctive segments of the genome. The outcome manifests as a striped pattern, facilitating comparisons with other samples (Nayana Ambardekar, 2022).

For DNA profiling or typing, recovering more DNA is crucial, especially in samples with few templates. Therefore, it is crucial to thoroughly inspect the buccal cavity before taking a sample and to take the sample by hand from at least two separate locations within the cavity (Puritan, 2022).

After the emergence of Corona virus disease in 2019 (COVID-19), the need for analyzing and comparing different swab materials used for COVID testing and forensic analysis plummeted (Pers. comm). Enhancing the probability of acquiring a meaningful DNA profile from a sample, whether gathered at a crime scene or within a laboratory setting, necessitates the utilization of a device proficient in collecting traces efficiently and selectively. This is imperative to safeguard their integrity, minimizing the risk of subsequent contamination and degradation. Moreover, it facilitates the successful retrieval of biological material for subsequent DNA analysis (Jennifer, *et al.*, 2019). These considerations underscore that the quality of a DNA profile hinges on both the overarching sampling technique employed by crime scene examiners or forensic investigators and the analytical procedures within the laboratory. Swabbing is one of the most adaptable and often utilized techniques. It is a non-intrusive and straightforward technique. The commonplace approach to retrieving biological material from crime scenes or acquiring reference samples, like buccal swabs, involves the prevalent method of using

swabs (Quaak, *et al.*, 2018). These swabs, categorized into three distinct design types, each serve specific purposes. They are:

- the wound swab, e.g. cotton swab, rayon swab;
- the flocked swab, e.g. nylon swab, oral swab;
- and the pad swab, e.g. foam swab (Vedant, *et al.*, 2023).

To make sure that the evidence gathered is accurate and reliable, it is essential to examine the swab devices used in forensic investigations to extract DNA. The selection of swab materials, design, and collection methods can have a big impact on how well and accurately DNA samples are collected. The preservation of DNA evidence is directly influenced by the material and design of the swab. Van Driessche, in his study, stated that carefully chosen swabs can help prevent contamination and degradation, ensuring that the DNA sample is kept pure and uncontaminated throughout the collection process. Different swab types and materials can produce different DNA yields (Van Driessche, *et al.*, 2019). By carefully examining swab devices, forensic investigators can select the best swab for the type of sample and surface, thereby increasing the DNA yield (Czarno, *et al.*, 2020).

In this study, commercially available swab devices used for COVID-19 testing were analyzed.

1.1 Aim and Objectives

The aim of this study is to assess DNA extraction efficiency using different swab devices made available for modern forensic investigations in Nigeria.

The objectives of the study are to:

- i. calculate the extraction and absorption capacity of the different swab devices used for the extraction of DNA from buccal mucosa;
- ii. measure the concentration of DNA extracted from the different swab materials using Nanodrop Spectrophotometer;
- iii. determine statistical significant difference using analysis of variance.

A biological sample, such as one containing DNA, proteins, or microorganisms, can be best obtained from the oral cavity. A buccal swab is the most widely used technique for collecting buccal cells because it is non-invasive, time-saving, and cost-effective. Other techniques include using a cytobrush and mouthwash (Yun-Seo, *et al.*, 2022).

1.2 Importance of this Study

Swabs are one of the most commonly used, single-use, devices in the medical industry, for DNA collection for most laboratory examinations, as well as in crime scene investigations. Variety of swab devices are used for this purpose. However, knowing which swab to choose and for which application is of great importance. Some swab materials tend to affect the quality and quantity of pure DNA extracted from samples collected. The effect of the swab material could lead to loss or minimum quantity of DNA extracted. On the other hand, a suitable swab device can further the efficiency and

purity of DNA extracted. The effectiveness of a sampling swab can be defined by its efficiency in extracting and retrieving substances. Nevertheless, there lacks a comprehensive study that systematically compares a spectrum of swab types in sampling various commonly collected biological samples from diverse surfaces. There is, therefore, need to evaluate the different swab devices available and used for sample collection in Nigeria, for their capacity to retain and release DNA material for subsequent analysis.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Aim, Design and Study setting

Swab materials commercially available from COVID-19 testing laboratories in Enugu metropolis and the Federal Capital territory (FCT Abuja), both in Nigeria, were evaluated. Designed for diverse biological, cleaning, or forensic applications, these swabs were specifically crafted for purposes like collecting bacteriological and viral specimens. In cases where multiple swabs with similar tip types were accessible from various manufacturers, the preference was given to the swab known to be utilized by forensic practitioners. The swab devices assessed and analyzed in this study are: Nasopharyngeal swabs, cotton swabs, oral swabs, and foam swabs (See Fig. 1 and table 1 for swab overview).

All samples adhered to the approved ethical standards and procedures for human testing. The collection and experimentation procedures commenced solely following the conclusion of the ethical review process, obtaining explicit written approval for this study from Enugu State University Teaching Hospital (ESUTH), Enugu, Nigeria.

2.2 Method of Sample collection

For the scope of this research, a single donor sample was employed. The donor's buccal cavity underwent examination for any open wounds or incisions, with gloves worn during the process. Subsequently, the internal cheek was swabbed for 60 seconds on each side using the swab tool, and this swabbing procedure was repeated thrice. Following this, the samples were placed into micro-tubes for DNA extraction. Throughout the study, four distinct tipped applicator swabs were utilized.

2.3 Description of the Swab devices used

Nylon flocked swabs consisting of brief strands of nylon fibers securely attached to a plastic shaft, these swabs showcase a design emphasizing their utility across diverse applications. The specimen is extracted completely and effectively because specimen collection is based on this structure's physical characteristics rather than the absorbance of a spun fiber.

Cotton Swabs are readily available and frequently employed. The utilization of cotton swabs for material collection may introduce challenges in extracting biological material from the cotton matrix. This arises due to the tendency of the cotton swab to dry post-collection, leading to the adherence of biological material to the swab.

Foam swabs possess a more porous structure compared to swabs made from polyester, rayon, and cotton. This particular type of swab distinguishes itself through its unique design.

2.4 DNA Extraction

Multiple buccal cheek samples from a single donor were isolated and subjected to extraction utilizing a DNA isolation/extraction kit, adhering strictly to the manufacturer's protocol. Subsequently, the obtained extract was utilized to evaluate the analysis of extraction and recovery for the swabs. To evaluate the quality of the extracted DNA samples, a 1% (w/v) Agarose gel Electrophoresis preparation was carried out.

2.5 Extraction Efficiency (EE)

Assessing the Extraction Efficiency (EE) involved pipetting 20 μL of DNA, extracted from a buccal sample using the Zymo Research DNA Isolation Kit, directly onto every swab. Following this, the swab head was separated, placed in a 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube, and subjected to vortexing for about a minute in 250 μL of TE-buffer. For each swab, a negative control was introduced by substituting 20 μL of DNA with an equal volume of TE-buffer.

The calculation for extraction efficiency (in %) was determined by:

$$EE = \frac{V_{\text{extraction}} \times [\text{sample}]}{V_{\text{applied}} \times [\text{origin}]} \times 100\%$$

Where [sample] denotes the measured concentration of the DNA sample (in $\text{ng}/\mu\text{L}$), V_{applied} represents the volume (in μL) added to the swab, $V_{\text{extraction}}$ signifies the extraction volume, and [origin] indicates the concentration of the original DNA extract (in $\text{ng}/\mu\text{L}$) obtained using the extraction kit (Bruijns, *et al.*, 2018).

Each swab underwent three measurements ($n = 3$).

2.6 Absorption Capacity (AC)

To determine the Absorption Capacity (AC), the swab, straight from the packaging, was positioned in a tube filled with TE-buffer for 1 minute, following which the tube was reweighed. The density of the TE-buffer solution (ρ) was then calculated and applied to ascertain the absorption capacity (in μL) of the swabs through the formula:

$$AC = \frac{\Delta(W_{\text{tube}} - W_{\text{swab}})}{\rho}$$

Where $\Delta(W_{\text{tube}} - W_{\text{swab}})$ represents the variance in average weight (in g) between the tube filled with buffer (W_{tube}) and the average weight (in g) of the tube with TE-buffer after the swab's removal (W_{swab}) (Bruijns, *et al.*, 2018). It's important to note that each swab underwent three measurements ($n = 3$).

2.7 Calculation of DNA concentration using Nanodrop Spectrophotometer

A NanoDrop spectrophotometer is a laboratory tool used to determine the purity as well as concentration of samples of proteins, RNA, and DNA. It measures the amount of light absorbed by a sample at various wavelengths using ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) absorbance (Strengths and Limitations of the Amazing NanoDrop™ Spectrophotometer, 2023).

The NanoDrop instrument (specifically, the NanoDrop1000 from Thermo Fisher Scientific) was used to find out how much DNA was in the samples. This was done by measuring how much light the samples absorbed at 260 nm. To make sure there was no contamination, negative controls were taken while conducting the DNA extraction efficiency experiment.

2.8 Statistical Analysis

The acquired data underwent One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to elucidate the distinctions among the various swab devices. The tests were set at 5% significant level ($P < 0.05$). Post hoc tests, Tukey honest significance differences (HSD), was used for pairwise comparisons.

3. Results

Absorption Capacity

Two swabs showed absorption capacity of 100 μL and 142 respectively (see Fig. 2 and table 2). The cotton swab and oral swab has large swabbing areas compared to the other swabs. Both the nasopharyngeal swab and the foam swab exhibit a considerably reduced swabbing area compared to the other swabs that were subjected to testing. Absorption capacity is usually dependent on size of swabbing area, as well as absorption/release properties of the swabs. A one-way ANOVA was carried out to assess the four distinct swab devices (refer to Table 3), uncovering a statistically significant difference among at least two swabs ($F(3, 8) = [887.27]$, $P = 0.00$). Following Tukey's HSD Test for multiple comparisons, it was ascertained that a noteworthy distinction existed between the nasopharyngeal swab and the oral swab ($P = 0.002$, C.I. = $[-15.95, -4.35]$).

Extraction Efficiency

Extraction efficiency experiments were carried out on all swabs irrespective of the absorption capacity value of those less than 100 μL . The extraction efficiency of the depicted swabs (as illustrated in Fig. 3) exhibited considerable variability, ranging between 28% and 82%, with the two nylon-flocked swabs demonstrating both low and high percentages. Notably, two swabs recorded values surpassing 50%, indicative of minimal DNA sample retention on the swab and consequently yielding high extraction efficiency. Remarkably, the recorded DNA concentrations for each swab demonstrated remarkable consistency. A one-way ANOVA was executed to assess the four distinct swab devices, revealing a lack of statistically significant differences among at least two swabs ($F(3, 4) = [0.16]$, $P = 0.91$). Following Tukey's HSD Test for multiple comparisons, it was confirmed that no significant differences were present between the various swab devices.

Concentration of extracted DNA using Nanodrop spectrophotometer

The Nanodrop Spectrophotometer was used to determine the concentration of extracted DNA before recovery from swab (Origin), and after recovery (Sample). The values obtained were compared to a control. There were variations in the concentration after DNA recovery from the swab. Origin was obtained directly from the buccal sample, extracted from the collection swabs, and then the concentration values were determined. Sample, on the other hand, was obtained by a re-extraction of Origin which was applied to sterile swabs, after which the concentration values were determined. These values were used to calculate the extraction efficiency off the different swabs.

Fig. 1a: Nasopharyngeal nylon flocked

Fig. 1b: Cotton swab

Fig. 1c: Oral Nylon flocked swab, full-tipped

Fig. 1d: Foam tipped swab

Fig. 2: The Absorption Capacity of the various swabs. Error bars indicate standard deviation

Fig. 3: The extraction efficiency of the various swabs. Error bars indicate standard deviation

Table 1. Overview of the swabs used in this research

S/N	Name	Type	Shaft
#1	Nasopharyngeal swab	Nylon flocked	Plastic
#2	Viral transporting media tube (VTM)	Cotton	Plastic
#3	Oral swab (full tipped)	Nylon flocked	Plastic
#4	Tekniswab Micro Tip	Foam	Plastic

Table 2: Performance of the swabs used in this research

Name	Type	AC (n=3), μL	EE (n=3), %	Concentration (n=3), $\text{ng}/\mu\text{L}$
#1 Nasopharyngeal swab stick	NF	100 \pm 3.4	43.4 \pm 3.8	1.3 \pm 0.1
#2 Viral Transporting Media Tube (VTM)	C	142 \pm 0.6	66.6 \pm 4.6	1.2 \pm 0.1
#3 Oral swab stick (full-tipped)	NF	91 \pm 2.5	81.9 \pm 5.2	1.4 \pm 0.1
#4 Tekniswab Micro Tip	F	49 \pm 1	28.4 \pm 3.1	1.1 \pm 0.1

Key: AC (absorption capacity), C (cotton), EE (extraction efficiency), F (foam), NF (nylon flocked).

Table 3: Analysis of Variance Results (ANOVA)

F-statistic value = 887.2799

P-value = 0

Data Summary

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error
Group 1	3	103.2667	3.4416	1.987
Group 2	3	142.8133	0.5658	0.3267
Group 3	3	93.11	2.5494	1.4719
Group 4	3	50	1	0.5774

Table 4: Statistical Summary

ANOVA Summary

Source	Degrees of Freedom DF	Sum of Squares SS	Mean Square MS	F-Stat	P-Value
Between groups	3	10385.7242	4361.9081	88.2799	
Within groups	8	39.3284	4.916		
Total	11	13125.0525			

4. Discussions

Swab devices used in forensic investigation vary in material and design, and this can affect DNA collection efficiency. For instance, cotton or synthetic swabs may absorb and release DNA differently. One study investigated the impact of different swab materials on DNA yield and quality, shedding light on the importance of material choice for efficient DNA collection (Silva, *et al.*, 2019).

The goal of criminal justice stakeholders and forensic scientists is to maximize DNA profiling performance. DNA profiling is based on interconnected procedures that are controlled by various partners, each with their own limitations and requirements. The efficacy of using a swab heavily reliant on capturing DNA is rendered futile if the genetic material is susceptible to destruction or loss during storage or the DNA extraction process, contingent upon the type of material involved. Optimal selection of technology for capturing biological traces necessitates considerations beyond mere analytical comparisons within a laboratory setting (Jennifer, *et al.*, 2019).

In a prior study, diverse swabs were assessed based on their collective collection and extraction efficiency (Verdon, *et al.*, 2014). There are a variety of swabs and DNA collection devices commercially available for COVID-19 testing. DNA recovery from swabs varies by manufacturer and fabric types. As per a recent study, the conventional cotton swab surpasses alternative swabs across a range of surfaces, emphasizing that the type and material of the swab can impact DNA recovery (Johannes, *et al.*, 2021). This aligns with earlier observations indicating that nylon-flocked swabs consistently failed to yield the maximum DNA output for samples extracted from various surfaces, including touch, saliva, or blood stains (Verdon, *et al.*, 2014). The effectiveness of nylon-flocked swabs is likely contingent on the nature of the sample and the particular characteristics of the surface under examination.

DNA efficiency in terms of sample collection, release, and overall yield has significantly improved since cotton swabs were replaced by nylon-flocked swabs. The likelihood of DNA traces remaining on nylon-

flocked swabs is lower, lowering the possibility of cross-contamination between samples. Due to this characteristic, they are especially useful in forensic applications (Krishan, *et al.*, 2020). The improved DNA retrieval achieved through the use of nylon-flocked swabs results in increased sensitivity and reliability in subsequent DNA analysis methods, such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and DNA sequencing (Cantu, *et al.*, 2021).

Previous research has shown that switching from cotton to nylon-flocked swabs improved DNA recovery for pure DNA and cartridge cases ((Bruijns, *et al.*, 2018 and Jansson, *et al.*, 2020). Although cotton swabs showcase absorption capacities similar to foam and nylon-flocked swabs, it is noteworthy that they have a lower propensity to release DNA during the extraction process (Bruijns, *et al.*, 2018 and Adamowicz, *et al.*, 2014). This is due to the tightly twisted compact cotton bud around the shaft. In a comparative study, flocked swabs was said to have had the maximum output of intact cells due to their capacity to release intact cells, as compared to cotton or dissolvable swabs, leading researchers to draw the conclusion that cotton swabs should not be used to gather biological samples (Jeremy, *et al.*, 2022). The quality of the DNA extracted from swab samples is crucial in legal proceedings. To ensure accurate results and support the criminal justice system, forensic professionals can examine swab devices to create and maintain quality assurance protocols (NCFS, 2021).

Conclusion

There are various swabs and DNA collection devices commercially available for COVID-19 testing. The amount of DNA obtained from swabs differed based on the manufacturer and the type of fabric used. In general, the greatest amount of DNA was retrieved from oral swabs (full-tipped), with cotton swabs coming next in terms of DNA recovery. Two of the examined swabs exhibited absorption capacity that exceeded 100 μ L, a phenomenon attributed to their morphology as determined by scanning electron microscope (SEM). It appears that the absorption capacity is more likely influenced by the tip dimensions and also by the arrangement of the fibers than the material constituting the swab. Notwithstanding their high absorption capacity, two examined swabs exhibited an extraction efficiency for pure DNA below 50%, whereas another surpassed the 50% threshold. The extraction efficiency ranged from 28.4% to 81.9%. Notably, the oral swab (full-tipped) designed for buccal samples demonstrated superior performance with an extraction efficiency of 82%, followed closely by the cotton swab with an extraction efficiency of 67%. This research demonstrates that the oral swab (full-tipped) exhibited optimal absorption capacity and extraction efficiency when compared with the other swab tips assessed in this study. The utilization of diverse swab tip types can exert a direct influence on the quantity of DNA retrieved, a crucial factor in forensic testing and DNA fingerprinting. Additionally, the method employed for sample collection holds a significant sway over the efficiency of DNA extraction. Both of these considerations underscore the importance of meticulous selection and standardized procedures in the collection and extraction processes to ensure optimal results in forensic applications.

List of Abbreviations

DNA- Deoxyribonucleic acid

COVID-19- Coronavirus disease (2019)

PCR- Polymerase chain reaction

SEM- Scanning electron microscope

Acknowledgements

I sincerely thank God Almighty and my parents, Mr and Mrs Nelson, for the guidance, support, encouragement and love. I want to specially thank Dr Christie O. Onyia, Ms Paschaleen Onyemaechi and Mr Uchenna Urom for their contributions, efforts, support and time. I want to thank my sisters and my friends who have contributed to the success of this work, I am so grateful.

The authors are grateful to the institution and every other body who made this research work possible.

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